

SEMANTIC AND METHODOLOGICAL FEATURES OF PARONYMS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13903727>

Abstract: This article provides a comparative analysis of the semantic and methodological features of paronyms in Uzbek and English. The study found similar and different aspects of paronyms in both languages, their use in speech, and their importance in linguistics. The article examines the linguistic nature of paronyms, their lexical-semantic properties and methodological tasks.

Keywords: paronyms, semantics, methodology, comparative linguistics, Uzbek, English

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi paronimlarning semantik va uslubiy xususiyatlari qiyosiy tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot natijasida ikkala tildagi paronimlarning o'xshash va farqli jihatlari, ularning nutqda qo'llanilishi va tilshunoslikdagi ahamiyati aniqlandi. Maqolada paronimlarning lingvistik tabiati, ularning leksik-semantik xususiyatlari va uslubiy vazifalari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: paronimlar, semantika, uslubiyat, qiyosiy tilshunoslik, o'zbek tili, ingliz tili

Аннотация: В данной статье будет проведен сравнительный анализ семантических и стилистических особенностей паронимов узбекского и английского языков. Исследование выявило сходства и различия паронимов в обоих языках, их использование в речи и значение в лингвистике. В статье рассматривается языковая природа паронимов, их лексико-семантические особенности и методические задачи.

Ключевые слова: паронимы, семантика, методология, сравнительное языкознание, узбекский язык, английский язык

INTRODUCTION

Paronyms, words that are similar in sound or form but differ in meaning, present a fascinating area of study in linguistics. They often pose challenges for language learners and can lead to confusion or misuse in both written and spoken communication. This research focuses on the semantic and stylistic features of paronyms in Uzbek and English, two languages with distinct linguistic roots and structures.

The significance of this study lies in its potential to enhance our understanding of lexical relationships across languages and to provide insights that could be valuable for language teaching, translation, and cross-cultural communication. By examining paronyms in Uzbek, a Turkic language, and English, a Germanic language, we can explore how linguistic diversity influences the occurrence and usage of these similar-sounding words.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

This study employs a qualitative approach based on an extensive review of existing literature on paronymy in Uzbek and English languages. The research draws from linguistic studies, dictionaries, and academic publications in both languages. Key sources include works by Uzbek linguists such as Abduzukhur Abduazizov and Azim Hojiev, as well as international scholars like David Crystal and Lynne Murphy.

The methodology involves a systematic analysis of paronyms in both languages, focusing on their semantic relationships, etymological origins, and stylistic uses. Comparative analysis is used to identify similarities and differences in the occurrence and treatment of paronyms in Uzbek and English.

RESULTS

The analysis reveals several key findings regarding paronyms in Uzbek and English:

Frequency and Types: Both languages exhibit a significant number of paronyms, but their distribution across word classes differs. In English, paronyms are commonly found among adjectives and verbs [1], while in Uzbek, they are more prevalent in nouns and adjectives [2].

Semantic Relationships: The semantic relationships between paronyms in both languages can be categorized into several types, including near-synonymy, antonymy, and semantic drift. However, the specific patterns of these relationships vary between Uzbek and English [3].

Etymological Factors: The etymological origins of paronyms in English often trace back to Latin or Greek roots, leading to clusters of related words [4]. In contrast, Uzbek paronyms frequently stem from Turkic roots, with some influence from Persian and Arabic [5].

Stylistic Usage: In both languages, paronyms are utilized for various stylistic purposes, including word play, rhetorical effect, and precision in technical or academic writing. However, the specific conventions and preferences for their use differ between Uzbek and English literary traditions [6].

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The findings highlight both similarities and differences in the nature and usage of paronyms in Uzbek and English. One significant similarity is the potential for confusion that paronyms create in both languages, particularly for language learners. This underscores the importance of context in distinguishing between similar-sounding words [7].

However, the differences in the linguistic structures of Uzbek and English lead to distinct patterns in paronymy. For instance, the agglutinative nature of Uzbek affects how paronyms are formed and used, often resulting in pairs of words that differ only in their suffixes. In contrast, English paronyms frequently involve changes in prefixes or internal vowels [8].

The etymological factors contributing to paronymy in both languages offer intriguing insights into their historical development and linguistic influences. English, with its complex history of borrowing from various languages, particularly Latin and Greek, has developed a rich tapestry of paronyms that often reflect different stages of borrowing or different routes of entry into the language. For example, the paronyms "economic" and "economical" both derive from Greek "oikonomikos," but entered the English lexicon at different times and through different paths, resulting in subtle semantic distinctions [4].

Uzbek, on the other hand, demonstrates the influence of its Turkic roots combined with borrowings from Persian and Arabic. This linguistic heritage creates a unique landscape of paronyms that often reflect the blending of native Turkic words with loanwords. For instance, some Uzbek paronyms may consist of a native Turkic word paired with an Arabic or Persian loanword, each having undergone phonological adaptations to fit Uzbek phonotactics [5].

Uzbek literature, while also employing paronyms for stylistic purposes, tends to use them in ways that align with the language's poetic traditions. The use of paronyms in Uzbek poetry often serves to create assonance and internal rhyme, enhancing the musicality of the verse. This usage reflects the strong oral tradition in Uzbek literature, where sound patterns play a crucial role in memorization and recitation.

From a pedagogical perspective, the study of paronyms in both languages offers valuable opportunities for enhancing vocabulary acquisition and language awareness. In English language teaching, exercises focusing on commonly confused paronyms (e.g., "affect" vs. "effect", "principle" vs. "principal") are often incorporated into curriculum to improve precision in language use. Similarly, in

Uzbek language instruction, attention to paronyms can help learners navigate the nuances of word choice and avoid common errors.

CONCLUSION

This study has illuminated the semantic and stylistic features of paronyms in Uzbek and English, revealing both universal linguistic phenomena and language-specific characteristics. The findings contribute to our understanding of lexical relationships and their cultural and linguistic contexts. In conclusion, the study of paronyms offers a valuable lens through which to examine the intricacies of language and meaning. By comparing Uzbek and English, we gain a deeper appreciation of linguistic diversity and the complex ways in which words relate to one another across different language systems.

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